

Varying Manifold Smoothness and Anti-Matter – 8 Theory

O Manor

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Abstract:

By analyzing the primordial coupling constants series and the main equation, it is possible to correlate the feature of manifold smoothness to anti-matter. The idea is to regard matter as curvature inversed in the direction, so the summation of both would account to zero or in other words, a smooth path on the matric on the varying manifold. The trait is applicable to both fermions and bosons, i.e. even amount of curvature and prime or one amount of curvature.

Introduction

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \quad (1.1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \quad (1.11)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (1.12)$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.13)$$

Since the photon is regarded as a prime amount of curvature $N_V = (+5)$ on the manifold, the matric position in which it appears on its not smooth, it is curved. To create a smooth path we need an additional photon, associated with $N_V = (-5)$, i.e. anti-matter.

$$[(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma - \gamma \quad (1.14)$$

The same would be applicable for the electron, or for any fermion cluster. In fact, it is possible to state that if there is any smooth path on the manifold, it is flattened by two inverse arbitrary variations that have the opposite sign. We can discretize and partition the arbitrary variation term δg of the main equation in two different ways. The first in equations () was presented in the thesis:

$$\left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \right] \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \right] \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.15)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0$$

We proved that there could be only two elements in the series and we associated two signs to those arbitrary variations

$$\delta g_1 \rightarrow (+) \quad (1.16)$$

$$\delta g_2 \rightarrow (-) \quad (1.17)$$

But the opposite would work exactly as well and the partitioned new series of arbitrary variations would vanish exactly to zero if :

$$\delta g_1 \rightarrow (-) \quad (1.18)$$

$$\delta g_2 \rightarrow (+) \quad (1.19)$$

That is to say, that each arbitrary variation has an inverse in sign that would not affect the overall result. Alternatively, in physical theories, that nature is invariant to sign, the laws would work just as well, that there is a so-called a "symmetry". Anti-matter and charge conjugation now can be presented as part of the 8 Theory as an arbitrary curvature inverse in direction, or physical meaning, the same but inverse in sign. The rules are invariant to shifting the signs in our theory, as the series would still vanish to zero either way.

References

[1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)